

Ajuts per a projectes d'innovació per a la millora de la qualitat docent en matèria de violència de gènere (INDOVIG 2020)

Justificació / Reporting

Memòria de les activitats del projecte / Report on project activities

Número d'expedient / File number

2020 INDOV 0003

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Dades del projecte / Details of the project

Títol del projecte de recerca / Research Project title

Mainstreaming Sexual and Gender-Related Violence sensibilities into university courses through Photovoice experiences

Transversalitzant la sensibilitat cap a les Violències sexuals i de gènere a les universitats a través de la practica del Photovoice

Universitat/centre / University/Centre

Universitat Rovira i Virgili

Breu resum del projecte (màxim 300 paraules) / **Brief summary of the project** (maximum 300 words)

This project aimed to create an internationally validated material to mainstream the work on Sexual and Gender-Related Violence (SGRV) within different disciplines in university courses, through an innovative teaching technique, Photovoice (PhV). PhV has been frequently used as a community-based participatory action research technique that, through photographs and narratives, has contributed to denounce communities' oppressions. As a pedagogical tool in classroom settings, it has fostered students' critical knowledge, reaching complex understandings of social problems. The use of our PhV proposal in teaching practice to address SGRV will have a transformative effect contributing to the awareness of teachers and students on the topic.

Our international (Catalan, Spanish, Australian, South African, Mexican and Argentina) and interdisciplinary (education, psychology, anthropology, health, sociology, philology, communication, politics, etc.) team have worked around three interconnected trends: (1) Coordination and management, (2) Action-Research and (3) Dissemination/Diffraction. Thanks to the expertise and the strong research background of the team members, we have design 5 pedagogical training videos on SGRV and PhV in order to train university teachers. Also, through the implementation of 3 Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) with students from different countries (Catalonia, Basque Country, Argentina and Mexico) and a collective international peer review process, we have been able to design a detailed teaching guide for implementing PhV in classroom settings.

Finally, we have disseminated our results in a website, international congress, the final project conference and in two academic articles, ensuring the spread of the materials produced within the framework of the project (all of them with Creative Common license).

Memòria de treball (Format lliure amb una extensió màxima de 3 pàgines) / **Working memory** (Free format with a maximum length of 3 pages)

Expliqueu: / *Explain:*

- les activitats desenvolupades en relació als objectius previstos i, si escau, les desviacions o no consecució dels objectius inicials i les mesures correctives aplicades / *the activities carried out in relation to the planned objectives and, where applicable, the deviations or non-achievement of the initial objectives and the corrective measures applied.*

- la metodologia utilitzada: descripció del procediment portat a terme per a desenvolupar el projecte / *the methodology: description of the procedure carried out to develop the project.*
- els resultats i l'impacte del projecte, realitzats i previstos: quines són les innovacions o les millores introduïdes en la docència segons els objectius assolits; com els coneixements adquirits han permès expandir les competències globals del sol·licitant i dels grups col·laboradors en la vessant de formació digital i pedagògica; quina és la previsió de difusió dels resultats i l'impacte en altres àmbits de coneixement i en la consecució dels Objectius de Desenvolupament Sostenible (ODS) de l'Agenda 2030 de Nacions Unides / *the results and impact of the project, carried out and planned: what are the innovations or improvements introduced in teaching according to the objectives achieved; how the knowledge acquired has made it possible to expand the global competencies of the applicant and the collaborating groups in the field of digital and pedagogical training; what is the forecast for the dissemination of the results and the impact in other areas of knowledge and in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda of the United Nations.*
- publicacions realitzades o previstes / *publications made or planned.*

Objectives 1.1 (Facilitate the collective, interdisciplinary and international production of knowledge) and 1.2 (Establish international networks of collaboration and transdisciplinary) have been completely achieved through the different collaborative and coordination activities that have been part of the project:

- Methodological exchange meetings (MEM): We carried out two online international meetings in order to evaluate with experts our previous experiences implementing PhV in classroom settings. Also, and in order to deepen and complexify the reflections developed during the second meeting with the Australian team, we sent them [videos analyzing our previous experiences](#) and some written specific inquiries, receiving written feedback back.
- Peer-to-peer collective evaluation of the teaching material (PTP): The drafts of the teaching guide and of the video content were sent to the rest of the team in order to be critically evaluated and having feedbacks for its improvements. The materials were also reviewed by other teachers interested in implementing photovoice in their classrooms, making it more adapted for professors who do not have a wide knowledge of SGRV or PhV.
- COILs experiences: The development of COILs was the result of a coordinated and collaborative work of different team members at international level, incorporating new researchers as Mila Amurrio of the UPV/EHU and Beatriz Soria of the UNCUYO, Argentina. The co-coord. facilitates the first COIL group and train the rest of the teachers involved with the support of the material produced. In addition, several meetings were held in which ideas and feelings were exchanged in the process of facilitating the different groups.

Changes implemented with respect to the original plan

The international and transdisciplinary nature of the project has not been devoid of challenges. The different schedules (ESP, AUS, ZA, MEX, ARG) and academic workloads have sometimes made coordination difficult. Also, the South African team disengaged from the project shortly after the methodological Exchange meetings. However, we included a new international collaborator Beatriz Soria from the UNCUYO (Argentina). She made a stay in URV in the framework of the project and collaborate actively in the COIL experiences.

We were able to realize a first detection of the needs that the teachers might have in relation to the implementation PhV on this topic (Objective 2.1) trough:

- Intragroup consultations: impressions and challenges regarding the use of photovoice on SGRV in the classroom were shared in two meetings and in written exchanging documents between the team members.
- Outgroup consultations: Informal meeting will be held with colleagues from different disciplines in order to understand their possible needs. This was also realized with some secondary school teachers in order to make the material more adaptable at this level.
- Focus groups: During the 6 hours training in photovoice methodology to the Consolidated Research Group on Teaching Innovation MideMe of the UB, a focus group was held to find out what needs or challenges professors considered they would face when implementing photovoice on SGRV in classroom.

Changes implemented with respect to the original plan

The focus group was not contemplated in the initial proposal, and we found it really useful, this consultation may continue in the future.

Objective 2.2 (to produce materials adapted to professors' needs and diverse disciplines) was fully achieved through the elaboration of materials and the objective 2.3 (to improve university professors' knowledge and ability to educate students to SGRV) will be an effect of the dissemination of those materials (the dissemination strategy will be wider explained with the objectives 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3).

- Collective and collaborative development of materials: for teacher training on SGRV and PhV. The elaboration process consisted of IP and Co-coord. making an initial proposal from the learnings of the previous experiences' evaluation and from the teacher needing detected. The full draft proposal of the guide was reviewed and improved thanks to the peer-to-peer collective evaluation and the learning of its implementation during the pilot COIL experience. The translation was carefully supervised by the linguistic team of the project. URV publications take care of the layout and subsequent publication as a part of Eina-e. After the analysis of the

detection of teachers' needs, we identified 4 sensible topics that had to be worked: the importance of the technique to tackle GRV; GRV in itself; Photovoice and Ethical issues. The team videos created video presentations to address these topics. First version of each video was shared with the team who proposed potential improvements. The linguistic team translate the PowerPoint presentation and we recorded them directly in the different languages of the project. We received technical support by the CRAI of URV. A 5th collective video was about suggesting topics to work GRV with PhV in different disciplines. In this case each of the three speakers used a different language and then we subtitled it in the other two languages.

Changes implemented with respect at the original plan
The guide was finally longer than we initially expected, therefore its translation and publication was more expensive. Also, we complemented our teaching materials with videos produced by students to make more visible the possible result of the work.

Our dissemination strategies allowed us to share the results in different contexts and spaces, both with students and teachers and also in academic spheres (congresses and scientific articles), promoting the use of PhV on SGRV within higher education institutions (Objectives 2.2, 3.1 and 3.3). Here the activities developed:

- COIL implementation and evaluation: A pilot test of our proposal to implement PhV on SGRV in classroom settings was carried out in three COIL groups, which were made up of students from Catalonia, Basque Country, Mexico and Argentina. Each group was composed of 7-10 students and was facilitated by different professors. The evaluation team designed two surveys, one for [students who experienced photovoice in COILs](#) and another for [students who attended to awareness-raising activities](#).

- Students involvement: In the COIL experience participate students of 6 different courses and degrees of universities. Once the group process was completed, the students carried out awareness-raising activities in their classes (around 250 students were involved) in which the photovoice processes were framed [and create a video to share it widely](#). We also had the collaboration of from a final-year psychology student who did her internship on the project, learning about GRV and PhV methodology. Another student from other university contacted us to prepare his final project on the methodology.

- Teachers involvement: Teachers originally not involved in the project experimented the use of the PhV in their university courses and beyond (an experience in second grade school was held) and all of them are interested in repeat the experience in the following years. Furthermore, we offered a course at the ICE of UB in order to train more teachers and in October another course will be developed in the US.

- Project final conference: Final conference was held on June 2nd 2021, with the participation of [FEAS; professors who implemented photovoice; students who experienced it in the COILs and where we also explain](#) the [main results and outputs](#) and [some reflections of our project's nature](#).

[General Director for the Eradication of Gender-Related Violence and the secretary of the Pedagogy Department of URV accompanied us opening the conference.](#)

- Lunch of the [Online exhibition](#) and [webpage](#). The exhibition team was in charge of the artistic and virtual dissemination of the material produced. In order to make the material more visible we decided to share it with other results of similar projects and create a collective webpage (the part of the other project is still in construction).

- Congress: [A poster](#) was presented in an online congress ([INNOVAGOGÍA 22](#)) and we also presented in the [Primer Congreso Internacional de Antropología Feminista](#). In September 2022 we will present the talk "Involving youth against Gender Related Violence through Photovoice: an international experience with Spanish, Mexican and Argentinian university students" in the [9ICCP Naples](#). In October 2022, we will also share our results in a course we will be offering in the US.

Changes implemented with respect at the original plan

We developed three COIL process instead two. Two professors did their research internships with us, actively collaborating in the project Dr. Mila Amurrio (from Basque Country) and Dr. Beatriz Soria (from Argentina). We also trained other teachers and had a final-year student actively participating in the project. We decided not to create two different set of videos but to merge them to create a more useful debate. Unfortunately, students did not use the Instagram account we had contemplated in our initial proposal.

All the activities previously described are orientated to achieve the objective 3.2 (Contributing to the transformation of the university culture on SGRV). In this line, our main outputs will make possible to multiply this effect:

a) A trilingual (CAT, ES, EN) teaching guide for the implementation of the photovoice technique in order to sensitize university students to SGRV.

b) A trilingual (CAT, ES, EN) sets of short videos in order to train university teachers. 1) [Photovoice: definition, theoretical framework and steps](#); 2) [An approximation to gender-related violences](#); 3) [Why is photovoice a good instrument to work SGRV?](#); 4) [Ethical recommendations for working with photovoice and gender related violence](#); and 5) [Addressing different typologies of gender related violence in classroom](#).

c) An on-line exhibition of students' photo-narratives.

d) The submission of the articles: Biglia B.; Cubero A. Mainstreaming the awareness about gender related violence through photovoice in universities is under review (since for the special issue Experiences from feminist pedagogies in the field of Education in [EDUCAR](#). / Luna, E.; Rubio, M. J. and Cubero A. Photovoice and critical pedagogy: A qualitative study applied to sexual and gender-related violence have been sent to [REIFOP](#).

e) An easily accessible [webpage](#) to all the material produced.

Informació per a la transferència dels resultats a la comunitat universitària i de recerca (Format lliure amb una extensió màxima de mitja pàgina) / **Information for the transfer of results to the university and research community** (Free format with a maximum length of half a page)

Aquesta informació podria publicar-se amb la finalitat de fer difusió de resultats dels ajuts INDOVIG / *This information could be published in order to disseminate the results of the INDOVIG grants.*

The PhV_SeGrEV teaching innovation project create an internationally validated material to mainstream the work on Sexual and Gender-Related Violence (SGRV) within different disciplines in university courses, through an innovative teaching technique, Photovoice (PhV). Our outcome are: (1) Improving university teachers' knowledge and abilities to educate students to SGRV; (2) Promoting the visibility of SGRV within the university; (3) Increasing future professional knowledge and skills to understand the dynamics and intersectional effects of SGRV; (4) Facilitating the integration of three languages in student learning processes; (5) Preparing students for assuming a global approach to reality through experiential cross-cultural learning; (6) Establish networks of scientific collaboration and transdisciplinary integration with an international team that will strengthen collaboration and fostering closer ties between four countries around the world; (7) Promoting Open Science and the integration of NTI in university courses

This feminist action research was based in four steps: Analysis of previous experiences; Initial detection of teachers needs; Creation and validation of teacher materials; Dissemination and diffractions. The material produced (in CAT, ES, EN) is available in our webpage for being re-used and applied in different courses this area:

- a) A teaching guide for the implementation of the photovoice technique to sensitize university students to SGRV.
- b) Five short content videos for teachers: 1) [Photovoice: definition, theoretical framework and steps](#); 2) [An approximation to gender-related violences](#); 3) [Why is photovoice a good instrument to work SGRV?](#); 4) [Ethical recommendations for working with photovoice and gender related violence](#); and 5) [Addressing different typologies of gender related violence in classroom](#)
- c) An [on-line exhibition](#) of students' photo-narratives.

Please let us know if you are using our material in your classroom and what does you think about them at phv.segrev@gmail.com.